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Evolution of cytokinin degrading CKX gene family in plants

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Cytokinins (CKs) are important plant hormones those regulate plant growth and development, including cell division, shoot meristem initiation, leaf senescence, chloroplast biogenesis, also regulate a host of additional development events such as *de novo* bud formation, release of buds from apical dominance, seed germination, CKs play vital role in the interaction of plant system with biotic and abiotic factors. Cytokinin oxidases/dehydrogenases (*CKX*) is quint essential in irreversible degradation of the isopentenyladenine, zeatin, and their ribosides in a single enzymatic step by oxidative side chain cleavage. To comprehend the evolutionary consequences of *CKX* genes during plant development, a meta-phylogenetic profile of at least 163 *CKX* amino acid sequences of monocot and eudicots plant species was analyzed. Bayesian phylogenetic algorithm-based mapping of 163 homologous and orthologous *CKX* sequences enumerated site-specific conservation scoring of individual amino acids. Paralogous gene divergences of *CKX* gene family had evolved essentially under the purifying selection along with the evolutionary trajectory of monocot and eudicot plant species. Gene structure and motif analyses indicated that most of the *CKX* genes showed a relatively conserved exon/intron arrangement and motif composition. Exon/intron organization in the *CKX* genes was mainly through gain/loss and insertion/deletions, which reflected the evolutionary diversification of these genes, that may also be related to their functional evolution. Expression profiling displayed *CKX1* gene expression in root tissues of different members of family Brassicaceae. These evidences strongly support the hypothesis that *CKX* gene might play an essential role in modulating CK levels in plant root organization; and propound its potential for the future crop improvement programs, particularly in the major oil-producing mustard species.